

Collatz-Type Maps with Alternating $3n \pm 1$

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Abstract

We study a Collatz-type map in which the odd-step alternates between $3n + 1$ and $3n - 1$. Computations up to 10^7 show that convergence depends strongly on the block length L , with a singular behavior at $L = 2$, where approximately half of the initial values enter a unique 44-cycle.

Keywords: Collatz conjecture, alternating map, periodic orbit, integer dynamics

MSC (2020): Primary 11B83; Secondary 37B20

1 Introduction

The classical Collatz map is defined by

$$T(n) = \begin{cases} n/2 & (n \text{ even}), \\ 3n + 1 & (n \text{ odd}). \end{cases}$$

We consider a modification in which the odd-step operation alternates between $3n + 1$ and $3n - 1$ according to a periodic sign sequence. The classical problem and its variants have been extensively studied (see, e.g., [1, 2]).

2 Definition

Let $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ and define a sequence $\{n_k\}$.

Fix a block length $L \geq 1$, and define

$$\varepsilon_k = \begin{cases} +1 & k \bmod (2L) < L, \\ -1 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Thus, the sign sequence consists of alternating blocks of L consecutive $+1$'s and L consecutive -1 's.

Define

$$T(n_k) = \begin{cases} n_k/2 & (n_k \text{ even}), \\ 3n_k + \varepsilon_k & (n_k \text{ odd}). \end{cases}$$

Importantly, the sign ε_k is updated at every step, regardless of parity. Thus, the phase evolves independently of the integer value, and the system is naturally viewed in the augmented state space $(n, k \bmod 2L)$.

3 Example

To illustrate the dynamics, consider the trajectory

$$9 \xrightarrow{+} 28 \xrightarrow{-} 14 \xrightarrow{+} 7 \xrightarrow{-} 20 \xrightarrow{+} 10 \xrightarrow{-} 5 \xrightarrow{+} 16 \xrightarrow{-} 8 \xrightarrow{+} 4 \xrightarrow{-} 2 \xrightarrow{+} 1.$$

Here, the transition $7 \rightarrow 20$ differs from the classical Collatz map, where one would have $7 \rightarrow 22$. The sign above each arrow indicates the phase, which evolves independently of parity.

4 Computational Results

We computed trajectories for all $1 \leq n \leq 10^7$.

Case $L = 1$

All tested initial values converge to 1.

Case $L = 2$

The convergence depends on the initial phase.

- Starting with $+1$: 5,179,334 failures out of 10^7 ,
- Starting with -1 : 5,160,310 failures.

Thus, the exception rate is approximately 51.6%–51.7%.

Although the number of exceptional initial values depends slightly on the phase, all such trajectories were observed to converge to the same 44-cycle. This result was already observed at $N = 10^5$, and remained unchanged upon extending the computation to $N = 10^6$ and $N = 10^7$.

The 44-cycle

Tracking the augmented state $(n, k \bmod 4)$ reveals a single periodic orbit:

$$\begin{aligned} 19 \xrightarrow{+} 58 \xrightarrow{+} 29 \xrightarrow{-} 86 \xrightarrow{-} 43 \xrightarrow{+} 130 \xrightarrow{+} 65 \xrightarrow{-} 194 \xrightarrow{-} 97 \xrightarrow{+} 292 \xrightarrow{+} 146 \xrightarrow{-} 73 \xrightarrow{-} 218 \\ \xrightarrow{+} 109 \xrightarrow{+} 328 \xrightarrow{-} 164 \xrightarrow{-} 82 \xrightarrow{+} 41 \xrightarrow{+} 124 \xrightarrow{-} 62 \xrightarrow{-} 31 \xrightarrow{+} 94 \xrightarrow{+} 47 \xrightarrow{-} 140 \xrightarrow{-} 70 \\ \xrightarrow{+} 35 \xrightarrow{+} 106 \xrightarrow{-} 53 \xrightarrow{-} 158 \xrightarrow{+} 79 \xrightarrow{+} 238 \xrightarrow{-} 119 \xrightarrow{-} 356 \xrightarrow{+} 178 \xrightarrow{+} 89 \xrightarrow{-} 266 \xrightarrow{-} 133 \\ \xrightarrow{+} 400 \xrightarrow{+} 200 \xrightarrow{-} 100 \xrightarrow{-} 50 \xrightarrow{+} 25 \xrightarrow{+} 76 \xrightarrow{-} 38 \xrightarrow{-} 19. \end{aligned}$$

This orbit consists of 44 distinct states and forms a closed cycle in the augmented state space.

For the $(++--)$ phase, every exceptional trajectory tested up to 10^7 was found to enter this cycle. No additional phase-distinct cycles were detected.

All trajectories reached either 1 or the 44-cycle within the step cutoff of 200,000.

Cases $L = 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8$

All tested initial values converge to 1.

5 Discussion

The behavior depends strongly on the block length.

- $L = 1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8$: convergence to 1,
- $L = 2$: large exceptional set converging to the 44-cycle.

For $L = 2$, the entire exceptional set up to 10^7 collapses into a single 44-cycle, suggesting the presence of a dominant attractor.

6 Conclusion

We observe a sharp dichotomy in behavior depending on L . The singular nature of $L = 2$ suggests a structural mechanism underlying the dynamics. This framework may provide a new perspective on the structure of the Collatz conjecture, potentially contributing to the broader study of Collatz-type dynamics.

Computational note. All computations were performed using Python. Trajectories for all $1 \leq n \leq 10^7$ were computed for each $L \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8\}$, with a step cutoff of 200,000; in practice, all orbits terminated well within this bound. For $L = 2$, the 44-cycle was already observed as the unique attractor at $N = 10^3$, and the result remained unchanged upon extending the computation to $N = 10^4, 10^5, 10^6$, and 10^7 .

References

- [1] J. C. Lagarias, *The $3x+1$ Problem and Its Generalizations*, American Mathematical Monthly, **92** (1985), 3–23.
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